

ISic3587

Honours for Trajan Decius

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2019-07-19 - Jonathan Prag edited the file based on autopsy and study for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

From the excavations in the agora of the early 1970s

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30606

Physical Description

Four joining fragments of a large white marble slab, with blue veins. The upper right corner is preserved intact, including sections of both the upper and right margin, but lower right, bottom, and all of the left side of the inscription are lost.

Dimensions

Height 45 cm

Width 35 cm

Depth 3.5 cm

Layout

Parts of six lines of Latin text are preserved. Guidelines are visible top and bottom of each line, and are closely observed; an additional guideline is visible above line 1.. The letters are 55-57 mm tall throughout, although the text becomes more condensed from line 3 onwards.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are roughly V-cut, with broad and pronounced vertical strokes, but generally much thinner horizontals. Serifs are pronounced but lightly cut and often include an element at an acute angle to the main stroke (e.g. on E, T, etc.). A consistently lacks a cross bar and on one occasion has a pronounced apex; P and R are open; O varies from almost circular to ovoid in form; E and F have horizontals of equal length. In line 3, I twice appears as a tiny letter, mid-line, presumably for reasons of space. Interpuncts are used throughout the text, but vary in type, including a standard three-pointed form, hederia, round dot, and simple three-sided outline shape.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-6: 55-57 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. [Imp(eratori) ·]
2. [Caio · M]essio ·
3. [Quin]to · Traiano ·
4. [Deci]o · Pio · Felici ·
5. [(vac.undefi)Aug(usto) ·]Res P(ublica) H,ā,!(aesinorum)[(vac.undefi)]
6. [Dev]ota [Numini]
7. [M]ai,ē[statiq][[(ue)] [eius]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy, after initial reconstruction by Scibona

Translation (en)

To the Emperor Caius Messius Quintus Traianus Decius, Pius, Felix, Augustus; the Res Publica of the people of Halaesa (set this up), vowed to his divine power and majesty.

Commentary

It is clear from the fragments that this is an honorific for the emperor C. Messius Q. Traianus Decius (reigned c. September 249 to c. June 251 AD) and restoration of the text can be attempted on that basis (for Decius' titles, see Wittig, K. 1932. RE 15, s.v. Messius no.9, col.1244-1286; Babcock, C. 1962. An inscription of Trajan Decius from Cosa. AJP 83: 147-158; and Peachin, M. 1990. Roman Imperial Titulature and Chronology, A.D. 235-284. Amsterdam: J.C. Gieben, at 32-34). Several considerations constrain the expansion. The first half of the second surviving line can only, realistically, contain the dative of the name Quintus. This serves more or less to define the width of the text and imposes limits on possible restorations. Given the space at the end of the first preserved line, which implies a corresponding indentation at the start of the line, it would be difficult to restore [IMP·CAES·C·M]ESSIO. This might be solved by restoring only IMP(erator), but the use of IMP(erator) alone is very unusual. An alternative solution is offered by the presence of a guideline above that of the first surviving line, which implies the presence of an additional line of text at the top of the inscription, which could be any of IMP, IMP·D·N·, or IMP·CAES· (although even IMP·CAES· looks over long, given the vacat at the top of what survives). Any such solution entails that the next line be restored as [CAIO · M]ESSIO ·, which is plausible given that Quintus is clearly spelled out in full. The following line is unproblematic, with Decius readily filling the available space. The precise expansion of the fourth surviving line depends upon the extent to which the text was centred, with space at start and end, and how far the name of the city was abbreviated. The alternative extremes are perhaps [(v.)AVG ·]RES P H,Ā,!(v.) and [AVG ·P·M·]RES P H,Ā,![AES], and the former is perhaps

preferable. The surviving letters of the last two preserved lines are readily compatible with the formula "devota numini maiestatique eius", found in a number of honorifics for Traianus Decius, such as AE 2002 no.465 [www.trismegistos.org/text/248065] and AE 1942/43 no.113 [www.trismegistos.org/text/204563] , although considerations of space affect the precise layout on the stone. A further formulation at the end, such as D(ecreto) D(ecurionum) is possible (as in ISic3590 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3590]), but not necessary.

The formula *res publica* is found in a number of Sicilian cities in the period from the later C2 AD to the early C4 AD, such as at Palermo/Panhormus (ISic0011 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0011] , ISic0012 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0012] , ISic0013 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0013] , ISic0015 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0015] , ISic0016 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0016] , ISic0017 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0017] , ISic0023 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0023] , ISic0024 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0024] , all imperial honorifics, late C2 AD to early C4 AD); at Solunto/Soluntum (ISic0047 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0047] , Fulvia Plautilla, 202-205 AD), at Termini/Thermae (ISic0108 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0108] , perhaps C2 AD), Tyndaris (ISic0679 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0679] , 198-211 AD), and Marsala/Lilybaeum (ISic0473 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0473] , C1 AD). A second example is now known at Halaesa (ISic3590 [http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3590] , not closely dated).

As with the other C2-3 AD imperial honorifics from Halaesa, there seems to be no evidence for the *damnatio memoriae* to which honorifics for Traianus Decius were often subjected elsewhere.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645666

Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.32

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-09-09): ISic3587. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4021591>

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